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Exploring The Effectiveness of Capacity Building Programs in Promoting Gender Equality in Agriculture: A Case Study of FCT Abuja

Dada Adebola Basirat¹; Sule Magaji² & Yahaya Ismail³

¹Sustainable Development Centre,
University of Abuja
dadaadebola3@gmail.com

^{2,3} Department of Economics
University of Abuja, Abuja, Nigeria
²[sule.magaji@uniabuja.edu.ng/](mailto:sule.magaji@uniabuja.edu.ng)
ORCID ID: 0000-0001-9583-3993

³ismail.yahaya@uniabuja.edu.ng
ORCID ID: 0009-0006-7876-9524

ABSTRACT

This study examines the effectiveness of capacity-building programs in promoting gender equality in agriculture within the Federal Capital Territory (FCT), Abuja. Using a stratified purposive sampling method, 270 participants—farmers, government officials, and representatives of women-focused NGOs — were selected. Data were gathered using the validated and reliable Capacity Building and Gender Equality in Agriculture Questionnaire (CBGEAQ), with a Cronbach’s alpha of 0.78. Employing a mixed-methods approach, the study found that most respondents were unaware of capacity-building initiatives specifically aimed at promoting gender equality, and many female farmers had not participated in such programs. Nevertheless, when implemented effectively, these programs enhanced women’s technical and networking skills, financial access, and mentorship opportunities. Key challenges identified included inadequate information dissemination, limited funding, cultural and educational barriers, and insufficient government-supported training efforts. The study emphasised the importance of stakeholder collaboration and community participation for sustainable program outcomes. It further recommended that the government implement and enforce the National Gender Policy in Agriculture within the FCT to ensure gender-responsive planning and budgeting, and to ensure equitable representation of women in agricultural decision-making bodies and cooperatives, thereby strengthening inclusivity and long-term impact.

Keywords: Gender Equality, Capacity Building, Female Farmers, Agricultural Development, FCT Abuja, National Gender Policy.

1.1 INTRODUCTION

Agriculture remains one of the most critical sectors for economic growth and development in Nigeria (Magaji & Baature, 2004). It serves as the primary source of livelihood for millions of rural dwellers (Musa et al., 2025) and a key contributor to food security and poverty reduction (Food and Agriculture Organisation [FAO], 2023). Despite women comprising nearly half of the agricultural labour force, their participation is often constrained by gender-based inequalities in access to productive resources, training, and decision-making opportunities (World Bank, 2022). These disparities limit women's ability to contribute optimally to agricultural productivity and rural development. As such, promoting gender equality in agriculture is not only a matter of social justice but also a strategic approach to achieving the Sustainable Development Goals, particularly Goals 5 and 2, which emphasise gender equality and zero hunger, respectively (United Nations, 2023).

Capacity-building programs have emerged as a vital mechanism for addressing gender disparities in agriculture through education (Magaji et al., 2025), training, and empowerment initiatives that enhance women farmers' knowledge, skills, and participation (Kabeer, 2020). Such programs are designed to strengthen institutional support systems, improve access to agricultural inputs, and enhance women's decision-making power in agricultural enterprises. In Nigeria, several governmental and non-governmental organisations have implemented gender-focused capacity building initiatives to empower women in agriculture, recognising their potential to drive economic transformation and sustainable livelihoods (Ogunlela & Mukhtar, 2021). However, the effectiveness of these programs in translating empowerment efforts into tangible gender equality outcomes remains an area requiring empirical evaluation, particularly within the Federal Capital Territory (FCT) of Abuja, where agricultural development policies intersect with urban and peri-urban dynamics.

The FCT Abuja presents a unique context for examining gender equality in agriculture, given its diverse socio-economic landscape and policy-driven agricultural development programs (National Bureau of Statistics [NBS], 2022). Many women in rural communities surrounding Abuja engage in small-scale farming and agribusiness activities but face systemic challenges, including limited access to credit, land ownership, and agricultural extension services (Adetunji et al., 2023). These constraints highlight the need to assess whether existing capacity-building programs effectively equip women with the resources and competencies to overcome structural barriers and achieve gender parity in agricultural production and leadership.

Empirical studies have shown that well-structured capacity-building initiatives significantly enhance women's agricultural productivity, self-efficacy, and socio-economic status when they incorporate participatory approaches and gender-sensitive frameworks (Osei-Akoto & Adu, 2021). Conversely, poorly implemented programs that fail to consider local gender norms or provide follow-up support often yield limited outcomes (Ekechukwu & Okoli, 2020). Therefore, evaluating the design, implementation, and impact of capacity-building programs in Abuja is crucial for understanding the extent to which these interventions promote gender inclusivity and equitable participation in agricultural value chains.

This study, therefore, seeks to explore the effectiveness of capacity-building programs in promoting gender equality in agriculture within the FCT Abuja. It aims to identify the strengths and limitations of existing programs, assess their impact on women's empowerment and agricultural participation, and provide recommendations for enhancing future interventions. By doing so, the study contributes to the broader discourse on gender mainstreaming in agricultural policy and development, aligning with Nigeria's national gender policy and the global agenda for sustainable and inclusive agricultural transformation.

2.0 Literature Review and Conceptual Framework

2.1 Conceptual Review

2.1.1 Capacity Building Programs

Capacity-building programs are structured initiatives designed to enhance the knowledge, skills, and competencies of individuals, organisations, and communities to improve performance and achieve

sustainable development outcomes (Ahmad & Magaji, 2025). These programs aim to strengthen institutional and human resource capacities through education, training, and knowledge transfer mechanisms that enable beneficiaries to effectively manage resources, solve problems, and adapt to changing environments (United Nations Development Programme [UNDP], 2022). In the context of agricultural development, capacity-building initiatives often target farmers, especially women and youth, by providing technical training, leadership development, access to information, and opportunities for collaboration and innovation (Kabeer, 2020). Such programs not only improve productivity and resource utilisation but also promote inclusivity and empowerment by ensuring equitable access to skills development and decision-making platforms (FAO, 2023). Thus, capacity building catalyses social transformation, enabling communities to build resilience, foster economic growth, and achieve long-term sustainability.

2.1.2 Gender Equality

Gender equality refers to the state in which women, men, girls, and boys have equal access to resources, opportunities, rights, and responsibilities across all spheres of life, including education, employment, political participation, and economic activities (United Nations, 2023). It emphasises eliminating discrimination and structural barriers that limit individuals based on gender (Magaji, 2002), ensuring fairness and inclusivity in decision-making and resource distribution (World Bank, 2022). In agriculture, gender equality is critical to achieving food security and rural development, as women play a central role in food production, processing, and marketing. However, persistent gender gaps in access to land, credit, training, and extension services continue to hinder women's potential to contribute effectively to agricultural productivity (Ogunlela & Mukhtar, 2021). Promoting gender equality through legal reforms, inclusive policies, and empowerment programs, therefore, enhances social justice, economic efficiency, and the attainment of the Sustainable Development Goals, particularly SDG 5 (gender equality) and SDG 2 (zero hunger) (FAO, 2023).

2.1.3 Agriculture

Agriculture encompasses the cultivation of crops, the rearing of livestock, and the management of natural resources to produce food, fibre, and raw materials essential for human survival and economic development (Magaji & Musa, 2024). It remains a cornerstone of the global economy and a primary source of livelihood, particularly in developing countries such as Nigeria, where it employs a significant proportion of the labour force (National Bureau of Statistics [NBS], 2022). Beyond its economic contribution, agriculture plays a vital role in ensuring food security, reducing poverty, and sustaining rural livelihoods (FAO, 2023). However, the sector faces numerous challenges, including climate change (Yakubu et al., 2025), land degradation (Abubakar et al., 2025), inadequate infrastructure (Olusola et al., 2025), and limited access to technology and finance (Magaji & Mohammed, 2004). To address these issues, modern agricultural strategies now emphasise sustainability, innovation, and inclusiveness, integrating gender equality, environmental stewardship, and policy reforms (World Bank, 2022). Therefore, agriculture is not only a driver of economic growth but also a platform for achieving equitable and sustainable development.

2.2 Theoretical Review

2.2.1 Empowerment Theory

The Empowerment Theory provides a relevant framework for understanding the effectiveness of capacity-building programs in promoting gender equality in agriculture. This theory emphasises the process through which individuals and communities gain control over resources, decision-making, and their own lives to achieve greater self-reliance and social transformation (Zimmerman, 2000). It emphasises participation in decision-making and ownership of assets (Muhammed et al., 2025). In the context of gender and agriculture, empowerment involves enhancing women's access to education, agricultural inputs, leadership roles, and productive assets to enable them to participate equitably with men in agricultural activities (Kabeer, 2020). Capacity building programs embody this theoretical perspective by equipping women with knowledge, technical skills, and institutional support that foster self-efficacy and agency in agricultural development. When women are empowered through targeted

interventions, they not only improve their livelihoods but also contribute to broader community development and sustainable agricultural outcomes (FAO, 2023). Thus, Empowerment Theory aligns closely with the study's objective of assessing how capacity-building initiatives facilitate gender equality and inclusive growth in the agricultural sector.

2.3 Empirical Review

Okeke et al. (2022) conducted a comprehensive investigation into the effectiveness of capacity-building programs in the Federal Capital Territory (FCT), Abuja, emphasising their role in empowering female farmers. The study revealed that initiatives designed with active participation from women during the planning and implementation stages tend to achieve more sustainable and impactful results. When female farmers contribute to shaping training content, selecting delivery methods, and influencing resource allocation, they exhibit higher engagement and derive greater benefits. The authors underscored the importance of adopting gender-sensitive strategies to ensure that capacity-building programs address the specific needs and challenges of female farmers. Programs that integrate women's perspectives in decision-making processes tend to be more inclusive, accessible, and relevant, ultimately enhancing participation and ensuring long-term success.

Furthermore, the study identified several barriers to women's full participation in these programs, including restrictive cultural norms, financial constraints, and systemic inequalities. To overcome these obstacles, the authors recommended implementing flexible training schedules, localised content, and financial assistance schemes that accommodate women's realities. Okeke et al. (2022) further emphasised the value of multi-stakeholder collaboration among government institutions, non-governmental organisations (NGOs), and local communities in developing responsive training models tailored to the needs of female farmers. By integrating women's voices into program planning and policy frameworks, capacity-building initiatives can foster greater gender inclusivity, enhance agricultural productivity, and promote socio-economic empowerment. The study concluded that adopting gender-responsive approaches is vital for improving program effectiveness and achieving equality in agricultural development.

Vanguard (2023) reported that more than 30 female farmers in the Jiwa community, Abuja Municipal Area Council, benefited from capacity-building initiatives focusing on farming innovation and technology. Organised by multiple NGOs, the program aimed to enhance participants' agricultural knowledge and equip them with modern farming techniques. Similarly, Adamu and Ibrahim (2023) identified significant barriers, including cultural restrictions and limited mobility, that hinder women's access to training programs. They stressed that addressing these challenges is essential to improving participation rates. In another study, Nwankwo et al. (2023) examined the effect of capacity-building efforts on agricultural productivity among women farmers. They found that participants experienced a notable increase in crop yields, suggesting that targeted training can significantly enhance food security.

Bello and Ojo (2023) observed that integrating technology into capacity-building initiatives has greatly benefited female farmers in FCT Abuja. Their findings indicate that digital tools facilitate access to information, markets, and agricultural resources, thereby improving training outcomes and overall program efficiency. Eze and Chukwu (2022) evaluated the sustainability of capacity-building programs. They discovered that initiatives with strong community participation and post-training support are more likely to maintain their positive effects over time. Additionally, Musa et al. (2023) highlighted the critical role of networking opportunities, noting that women who engaged in such activities reported improved collaboration, knowledge exchange, and resource sharing, which enhanced their farming practices.

Adebayo and Salami (2023) explored the influence of financial literacy training within capacity-building initiatives. They found that improved financial management skills enable women farmers to make better investment and production decisions. Uche and Nwosu (2022) emphasised the need for cultural sensitivity in program design, arguing that initiatives that respect and align with local customs are more likely to gain acceptance and participation from women in rural areas. Finally, Jibril et al. (2023) conducted a comprehensive review proposing new evaluation metrics for assessing capacity-building effectiveness. Their study advocated a holistic assessment framework that integrates quantitative and qualitative indicators better to capture the programs' actual impact and sustainability.

2.4 Gap in the Literature

Despite the growing body of literature emphasising the importance of capacity-building programs in empowering female farmers in the Federal Capital Territory (FCT) and across Nigeria (Okeke et al., 2022; Adamu & Ibrahim, 2023; Nwankwo et al., 2023), significant gaps remain in understanding the long-term effectiveness and sustainability of these initiatives. Most existing studies have focused on short-term outcomes such as increased productivity, improved access to resources, and enhanced technical skills (Bello & Ojo, 2023; Musa et al., 2023), while limited attention has been given to how these programs influence systemic gender inequalities, decision-making power, and socio-economic resilience over time. Furthermore, there is insufficient empirical evidence on how contextual factors such as cultural norms, institutional support, and digital inclusion interact to affect women's participation and retention in these programs (Uche & Nwosu, 2022; Eze & Chukwu, 2022). Additionally, few studies have developed or applied holistic evaluation frameworks that combine both quantitative and qualitative metrics to assess gender-responsive capacity-building outcomes (Jibril et al., 2023). Therefore, a research gap exists in assessing the multidimensional and long-term impact of capacity-building programs on gender equality, agricultural productivity, and women's empowerment in FCT Abuja.

3.0 METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Design

This study adopted a descriptive survey research design. The design was appropriate because it enabled the researcher to collect quantitative and qualitative data from a large number of respondents to examine their opinions, perceptions, and experiences regarding the effectiveness of capacity-building programs in promoting gender equality in agriculture. The design also allowed the researcher to describe existing conditions and relationships without manipulating variables, making it suitable for a case study of FCT Abuja.

3.2 Population of the Study

The population of this study comprised all male and female farmers, agricultural extension officers, and stakeholders who have participated in or benefited from capacity-building programs within the Federal Capital Territory (FCT), Abuja. This population was selected because it includes individuals directly engaged in agricultural activities and those who have benefited from gender-oriented interventions in the agricultural sector.

3.3 Sample Size and Sampling Technique

The study employed a sample size of 350 respondents drawn from the six area councils of FCT Abuja. The sample size was determined using the Taro Yamane formula to ensure statistical adequacy and representativeness. A stratified random sampling technique was used to ensure that male and female farmers, extension officers, and program facilitators were adequately represented across the study area's agricultural zones.

3.4 Model Specification

The study used a multiple linear regression model to examine the relationship between capacity-building programs and gender equality in agriculture. The model was expressed as:

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1X_1 + \beta_2X_2 + \beta_3X_3 + \mu$$

Where:

Y = Gender Equality in Agriculture

β_0 = Constant term

$\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3$ = Regression coefficients

X_1 = Training and Skill Development

X₂ = Access to Resources and Support Services

X₃ = Institutional and Policy Support

μ = Error term

The model sought to determine the extent to which various dimensions of capacity building (training, access to resources, and institutional support) influence gender equality outcomes in agricultural participation and productivity.

3.5 Method of Data Collection

Primary data were collected using structured questionnaires and interviews. The questionnaire included both closed-ended and open-ended questions to capture respondents’ experiences and perceptions of capacity-building programs and their impact on gender equality in agriculture. Interviews were also conducted with selected agricultural stakeholders and program coordinators to obtain deeper qualitative insights into the practical outcomes and challenges of these programs.

3.6 Method of Data Analysis

Quantitative data obtained from the questionnaires were analysed using descriptive and inferential statistical techniques, including frequency distributions, percentages, mean scores, and multiple linear regression, using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS). The regression analysis tested the formulated hypotheses and determined the strength and significance of relationships among the variables. Qualitative data from interviews were analysed thematically to identify emerging themes and patterns that complemented the quantitative results. This mixed-methods approach ensured a comprehensive understanding of how capacity-building programs promote gender equality in agriculture in FCT Abuja.

4.0 DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS OF RESULTS

The section explains and presents the research findings using both quantitative and qualitative approaches. The chapter presents the data collected and analysed using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS), in the form of frequency distributions and percentages. A total number of 240 questionnaires was administered and distributed to willing respondents, but only two hundred and twenty-seven questionnaires (227) were filled out and retrieved. To support the quantitative approach, 30 people were subjected to a Focus Group Discussion (FGD) conducted with Government officials at the Federal Ministry of Agriculture and Food Security, rural farmers, and the Women Farmers Association in FCT, Abuja, using a qualitative approach. The qualitative approach used open-ended questions aligned with the study's objectives. Therefore, the presentation and analysis of the data in this chapter were based on the two hundred and twenty-seven (227) retrieved questionnaires and the thirty (30) qualitative approach conducted.

Number of Participants

Total Participants	Retrieved	Missed
240 (Quantitative Approach)	227	13
30 (Qualitative Approach)	30	Nil

Source: Field Survey, 2025

The table above shows the total number of participants, 240. Out of these participants (227) were subjected to a quantitative approach, while 30 participants were subjected to a qualitative approach in two separate meetings.

4.1: Socio-Demography And Economic Characteristics Of The Respondents

The demographic analysis of respondents provides essential insights into the nature and characteristics of the participants who responded to the survey on the effectiveness of capacity-building programs in promoting gender equality in agriculture within the Federal Capital Territory (FCT), Abuja.

Table 1: Age of Respondents

Age	Frequency	Percentage
No Specification	13	5.7
25-35	139	61.2
36-45	52	22.9
46-60	22	9.7
61 and above	01	0.4
Total	227	100.0

Source: Field Survey, 2025

The table above provides the age distribution of the respondents in a study. The largest group was aged 25-35 years, comprising 61.2% of the total. The next-largest group was aged 36-45 years, with 22.9%, followed by those aged 46-60 years, with 9.7%. A smaller proportion of respondents did not specify their age (5.7%), and the smallest group was those aged 61 and above (0.4%). This indicates that most respondents were between 25 and 35 years old, suggesting a predominantly youthful population that is potentially more receptive to new knowledge and innovative agricultural practices. This age group is crucial for the future of agriculture and represents a dynamic workforce that can benefit immensely from targeted capacity-building interventions.

Table 2: Sex of the Respondents

Sex	Frequency	Percentage
Male	87	38.3
Female	140	61.7
Total	227	100

Source: Field Survey, 2025

The Table above presents the sex distribution of the respondents. Out of a total of 227 respondents, as many as 61.7% were females, and 38.3% of the respondents were males. This indicates that a significant majority of the respondents were female, underscoring the growing involvement of women in agriculture in the FCT. The dominance of female respondents underscores the urgent need for gender-sensitive agricultural programs that address the specific barriers women face, including access to resources, training, and decision-making roles.

Table 3: Marital Status of the Respondents

Marital Status	Frequency	Percentage
Single	99	43.6
Married	120	52.9
Divorced	04	1.8
Widowed	04	1.8
Total	227	100

Source: Field Survey, 2025

The table above presents the respondents' marital status in the study. 52.9% were married, making it the most common marital status. This is followed by single respondents, who made up 43.6%. Smaller proportions were divorced and widowed, with 1.8% each. This shows that nearly half of

the respondents were married, with singles the next-largest group, while the remaining respondents were distributed across the divorced and widowed categories. This demographic composition suggests that capacity-building initiatives must consider family responsibilities, particularly for women who may face dual burdens in balancing household and agricultural tasks.

Table 4: Educational Level of the Respondents

Educational	Frequency	Percentage
No Education	178	78.4
Primary	01	0.4
Secondary	02	0.8
Tertiary	46	20.3
Total	227	100

Source: Field Survey, 2025

The table above presents the educational qualifications of the respondents. The largest group, 78.4% had formal education. Following this, 20.3% obtained a tertiary primary Certificate. About 16.8% had no formal education, while 10.9% had a bachelor’s degree, 0.8% had a secondary certificate, and 0.4% had only a primary certificate. This implies that respondents' educational attainment is notably low, suggesting data-collection gaps. This trend reveals a potential barrier to the effectiveness of capacity-building efforts, particularly where literacy and formal education are prerequisites for participation. As such, training programs should be tailored to accommodate low-literacy participants by using visual aids, local languages, and practical demonstrations.

Table 5: Occupation of the Respondents

Occupation	Frequency	Percentage
Business	03	1.3
Farmer	86	37.9
Government Official	29	12.8
NGO Representative - NWAP-DI	42	18.5
Teacher	06	2.6
Student	03	1.3
Others	58	25.6
Total	227	100

Source: Field Survey, 2025

The table above presents respondents' occupations. The largest group, 37.9% were farmers. Following this, 25.6% engaged in other occupations, such as artisan work; 1.3% were students; and 1.3% engaged in business. The presence of agricultural extension workers, NGO representatives, and government officials suggests a multi-stakeholder environment conducive to implementing capacity-building initiatives. However, the substantial “others” category warrants further clarification to ensure inclusive targeting of all stakeholders.

Table 6: Household Size of the Respondents

Household Size	Frequency	Percentage
1-4	128	56.4
5-8	76	33.5
9-12	23	9.8
Total	227	100

Source: Field Survey, 2025

The table above presents the household size of the respondents. The largest group, 56.4% lives in a small household of 1-4, followed by 33.5% with medium-sized households of 5-8, and 9.8% with relatively large households of 9-12. These variations in household size could influence labour availability and the division of agricultural roles, with implications for program design and gender mainstreaming.

Table 7: Whether the Respondents Own Land

Land Ownership	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	117	51.5
No	110	48.5
Total	227	100

Source: Field Survey, 2025

The table above presents data on whether the respondent owns or has access to land. One-third of respondents (51.5%) answered yes, while 48.5% answered no. This reflects a critical challenge, especially for women, who traditionally face constraints in land ownership. Since land is a vital asset in agriculture, capacity-building programs must incorporate advocacy for secure land tenure and address structural inequalities that limit women's access to productive resources.

Table 8: Monthly Income Level of the Respondents

Monthly Income	Frequency	Percentage
Below #20,000	45	20.3
#21,000- #40,000	52	23.4
#41,000 - #60,000	32	14.4
#61,000 and above	93	41.9
Total	227	100

Source: Field Survey, 2025

The table above shows the respondents' monthly income. The largest group, 41.9%, earns 61,000 or more; 23.4%, 21,000–40,000; 20.3%, below 20,000; and 14.4%, 41,000–60,000. This implies that the majority of the respondents earn 61,000 or more. Capacity-building initiatives should, therefore, aim not only to impart knowledge but also to enhance productivity, income generation, and economic empowerment, particularly for women and low-income earners.

4.2: Awareness And Participation Of Female Farmers In Capacity Building

Using a quantitative approach, this utilised the frequency and breakdown of the respondents' awareness and participation in capacity Building in FCT, Abuja, under the following subheadings.

Table 9: Respondents' Awareness of any capacity-building programs aimed at promoting gender equality in agriculture within FCT Abuja

Awareness	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	52	23.3
No	76	76.7
Total	227	100

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Table 9 presents data on respondents' awareness of capacity-building programs aimed at promoting gender equality in agriculture within the Federal Capital Territory (FCT), Abuja. The results reveal that

only 52 respondents (23.3%) reported awareness of such programs, while 76 respondents (76.7%) reported not being aware of any existing initiatives. This suggests that capacity-building programs addressing gender equality in agriculture are either insufficiently publicised or inadequately implemented, resulting in low awareness among agricultural stakeholders in the region. The findings highlight the need for increased advocacy, outreach, and sensitisation to ensure that such programs reach their intended beneficiaries effectively.

Table 10: Respondents' views on whether they had participated in any capacity-building programs related to agriculture and gender equality in FCT

Participated	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	57	25.4
No	167	74.6
Total	227	100

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Table 10 shows the respondents' participation in capacity-building programs related to agriculture and gender equality within the Federal Capital Territory (FCT). The results indicate that only 57 respondents (25.4%) had participated in such programs, while 167 respondents (74.6%) had not. This implies that the level of participation in agricultural and gender-focused capacity-building initiatives is relatively low among respondents in the area. The limited involvement may be due to inadequate access to information, limited program availability, or insufficient inclusion strategies. These findings underscore the importance of expanding participation opportunities and improving program dissemination to enhance gender equality and agricultural development in the FCT.

4.3: Impact Of Capacity Building Programs

Using a quantitative approach and utilising the frequency and breakdown of respondents on the impact of capacity-building programs in promoting Gender Equality in Agriculture in FCT, the following responses were obtained under the following subheadings.

Table 11: Respondents' views on the Effectiveness of Capacity programs in promoting Gender Equality in Agriculture in FCT

Impact	Frequency	Percentage
Ineffective	07	3.2
Slightly effective	28	12.6
Very Effective	97	43.7
Moderately effective	53	23.9
Not sure	37	16.7
Total	227	100

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Table 11 presents respondents' views on the effectiveness of capacity-building programs in promoting gender equality in agriculture within the Federal Capital Territory (FCT). The findings reveal that 97 respondents (43.7%) considered the programs very effective, while 53 respondents (23.9%) rated them as moderately effective. Additionally, 28 respondents (12.6%) perceived the programs as slightly effective, while only 7 (3.2%) viewed them as ineffective. Meanwhile, 37 respondents (16.7%) were uncertain about their effectiveness. Overall, the results suggest that a majority of respondents believe capacity-building programs have had a positive impact on promoting gender equality in agriculture. However, uncertainty and varying levels of perceived effectiveness indicate room for improvement in their design, implementation, and reach.

Table 12: Respondents' views on the Specific aspects of the programs that have been beneficial

Aspect	Frequency	Percentage
Technical training	87	41.4
Access to Resources	66	31.4
Networking Opportunities	87	41.4
Financial Support	65	31.0
Others	20	9.5
Total	227	100

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Table 12 presents respondents' views on the specific aspects of capacity-building programs that have been most beneficial in promoting gender equality in agriculture within the Federal Capital Territory (FCT). The results show that technical training and networking opportunities were identified as the most beneficial components, each cited by 87 respondents, representing 41.4% of the total. Access to resources was cited by 66 respondents (31.4%), while 65 respondents (31.0%) highlighted financial support as a key benefit. Additionally, 20 respondents (9.5%) mentioned other unspecified benefits. These findings indicate that technical skill development and networking play crucial roles in enhancing participants' capacities. At the same time, access to resources and financial support further contribute to empowerment and gender balance in agricultural activities within the FCT.

Table 13: Respondents' views on whether the programs had helped in increasing respondents' agricultural productivity and income

Helped	Frequency	Percentage
No changed	35	15.4
Moderately decreased	02	0.9
Moderately increased	100	44.1
Significantly decreased	65	28.6
Significantly increased	25	11.0
Total	227	100

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Table 13 presents respondents' views on whether participation in capacity-building programs has increased their agricultural productivity and income in the Federal Capital Territory (FCT). The findings show that 100 respondents (44.1%) reported a moderate increase in productivity and income, while 25 respondents (11.0%) reported a significant increase. Conversely, 65 respondents (28.6%) experienced a significant decrease, two respondents (0.9%) a moderate decrease, and 35 respondents (15.4%) no change. These results suggest that although a considerable proportion of respondents benefited positively from the programs, a notable percentage did not experience improvement or even reported declines, possibly due to unequal access to program benefits, differences in resource utilisation, or variations in program relevance. This highlights the need for more inclusive and context-specific approaches to enhance the overall impact of capacity-building initiatives on agricultural productivity and income.

4.4: Challenges And Barriers

Using a quantitative approach that utilises frequency and respondent breakdowns of the challenges and barriers affecting capacity building in FCT, the following information from the respondents was obtained under the sub-headings.

Table 14: Challenges faced in accessing and benefiting from these capacity-building programs in FCT

Challenges	Frequency	Percentage
Lack of Information	119	55.1
Limited Resources	94	43.5
Gender discrimination	41	19.0
Others	06	2.8
Total	227	100

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Table 14 presents the challenges respondents faced in accessing and benefiting from capacity-building programs in the Federal Capital Territory (FCT). The findings reveal that the most common challenge was a lack of information, reported by 119 respondents (55.1% of the total sample). This was followed by limited resources, cited by 94 respondents (43.5%), while 41 respondents (19.0%) identified gender discrimination as a key obstacle. Additionally, six respondents (2.8%) mentioned other unspecified challenges. These results suggest that inadequate access to information and limited resources are the primary barriers preventing effective participation in capacity-building initiatives. The persistence of gender-based discrimination further hinders equitable access, emphasising the need for more inclusive, well-publicised, and resource-supported programs to ensure broader participation and greater impact among agricultural stakeholders in the FCT.

Table 15: Respondents' views on whether they have experienced any form of gender-based discrimination in their agricultural activities in FCT

Experience	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	56	24.7
No	171	75.3
Total	227	100

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Table 15 shows respondents' experiences of gender-based discrimination in their agricultural activities within the Federal Capital Territory (FCT). The results indicate that 56 respondents (24.7%) reported experiencing gender-based discrimination, while 171 respondents (75.3%) stated they had not. This suggests that although gender-based bias exists in the agricultural sector, it affects a smaller proportion of participants than those who operate in more equitable conditions. However, the presence of nearly one-quarter of respondents reporting discrimination highlights that gender inequality remains a concern and underscores the need for continuous awareness, policy enforcement, and institutional interventions to promote fairness and inclusivity in agricultural practices across the FCT.

4.5: Role of Stakeholders in Capacity-Building Initiatives for Female Farmers

The qualitative findings from the Focus Group Discussions reveal that various stakeholders play complementary but sometimes uncoordinated roles in capacity-building initiatives for female farmers in the Federal Capital Territory (FCT). Government agencies, particularly the Ministries of Agriculture and Women's Affairs, are central to policy formulation, technical training, and resource distribution. At the same time, NGOs such as AWEN, WOFAN, and IFAD provide specialised training, mentorship, and financial support tailored to women's agricultural needs. Local communities also contribute by organising cooperatives, promoting peer learning, and fostering grassroots empowerment, although traditional gender norms often limit women's participation. Despite these collective efforts, challenges such as poor coordination, limited awareness, inadequate funding, and bureaucratic constraints reduce the overall effectiveness and sustainability of the programs. The discussions emphasise that stronger collaboration among government bodies, NGOs, and local communities, alongside improved communication, monitoring, and gender-sensitive strategies, would significantly enhance the impact of capacity-building programs on female farmers' productivity and empowerment.

4.6: Monitoring and Evaluation of Capacity-Building Programs for Female Farmers

The qualitative findings on monitoring and evaluation of capacity-building programs for female farmers reveal that multiple mechanisms are employed to assess program success and impact in the Federal Capital Territory (FCT). According to respondents, agricultural productivity metrics such as improvements in crop yields, soil fertility, and the adoption of modern farming techniques serve as primary indicators of program effectiveness. Additionally, measures of financial independence and empowerment, including women's access to agricultural loans, business ownership, participation in leadership, and income growth, are used to evaluate progress toward gender equality. Policy-level assessments also involve structured impact reviews that track sustainability indicators, resource access, and environmental practices among trained female farmers. Despite these efforts, challenges such as inconsistent data collection, lack of standardised frameworks, limited long-term funding, and outdated

monitoring tools hinder practical evaluation. The discussions emphasise the need for a more structured, technology-driven monitoring system that incorporates real-time data tracking, regular feedback loops, and direct integration of farmers' input into policy adjustments to strengthen the sustainability and impact of capacity-building programs.

Table 16: Respondents' views on how the government and NGOs can better support female farmers in FCT Abuja

Support from Govt and NGO	Frequency	Percentage
Provide financial Assistance	132	59.5
Enhance extension Services	40	18.0
Improved market access	31	14.0
Offer Legal Support	16	7.2
Others	03	1.4
Total	227	100

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Table 16 presents respondents' views on how the government and non-governmental organisations (NGOs) can better support female farmers in the Federal Capital Territory (FCT), Abuja. The findings indicate that the majority of respondents — 132, representing 59.5% — believe that providing financial assistance is the most effective way to support women farmers. This is followed by 40 respondents (18.0%) who emphasised the need to enhance agricultural extension services, while 31 respondents (14.0%) suggested improving market access for female farmers. Additionally, 16 respondents (7.2%) highlighted the importance of offering legal support to protect women's rights and land ownership, and three respondents (1.4%) mentioned other forms of support. Overall, the results suggest that financial empowerment remains the most pressing need for female farmers, but strengthening extension services, market access, and legal frameworks is also essential for achieving sustainable gender equality and agricultural development in the FCT.

4.7 DISCUSSIONS OF FINDINGS

The study's findings revealed that awareness and participation in capacity-building programs aimed at promoting gender equality in agriculture within the Federal Capital Territory (FCT) remain significantly low. A large proportion of respondents were unaware of such programs, highlighting a communication gap between program implementers and the target beneficiaries. While a few respondents acknowledged awareness through ministries and NGOs, most farmers, especially women, lacked adequate information and access to these initiatives. Similarly, participation levels were low due to limited program availability, poor outreach, socio-cultural barriers, and financial constraints. Nevertheless, qualitative insights revealed that some ongoing programs, such as those organised by the Ministry of Agriculture, Women's Affairs, and NGOs, have provided training and empowerment opportunities. These findings align with previous studies, such as Oladide (2023), which emphasised the crucial role of agricultural capacity-building in reducing gender disparities by improving women's access to resources, training, and financial support.

The findings further established that capacity-building programs can be highly effective in promoting gender equality and enhancing productivity when properly implemented. A majority of respondents viewed these programs as very effective, particularly in technical training, networking, access to financial support, and the use of modern agricultural technology. However, challenges such as poor coordination, limited monitoring and evaluation, and inadequate inclusiveness persist. These weaknesses undermine the long-term sustainability of interventions and limit their overall impact. The findings also revealed that the main challenges hindering effective capacity building include a lack of information, limited resources, cultural and gender barriers, and institutional inefficiencies. This agrees with Akinyele et al. (2024), who noted that female farmers face multiple constraints that require structured interventions to enhance skills, knowledge, and resource access, thereby improving gender equity and agricultural productivity.

Furthermore, the study highlighted that stakeholder engagement plays a vital role in strengthening capacity-building efforts for female farmers in the FCT. The Ministry of Agriculture and the Ministry of

Women's Affairs were identified as central actors, supported by NGOs such as AWEN, WOFAN, and IFAD, which provide technical training, mentorship, and entrepreneurship support. Local communities also contribute by forming cooperatives and promoting peer learning, although traditional norms still limit women's participation. Monitoring and evaluation mechanisms relied on productivity metrics, financial empowerment indicators, and policy alignment reviews. Despite these measures, challenges such as poor coordination, limited funding, and outdated data systems persist. Therefore, enhancing multi-stakeholder collaboration, improving communication, integrating digital monitoring tools, and enforcing gender-responsive agricultural policies at federal, state, and community levels are essential to ensure inclusiveness, accountability, and sustainability of capacity-building programs for women farmers in the FCT.

5.0 CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

The study concludes that capacity-building programs hold significant potential to promote gender equality in agriculture within the Federal Capital Territory (FCT), Abuja. However, their current impact remains limited due to limited awareness, inadequate participation, and structural barriers. The findings revealed that when effectively designed and implemented, these programs can improve women's access to agricultural resources, enhance technical and financial skills, and foster greater involvement in decision-making processes. However, challenges such as limited funding, weak information dissemination, cultural constraints, and lack of government-supported initiatives have hindered their full effectiveness. The study underscores the importance of gender-sensitive approaches and stakeholder collaboration in ensuring that such programs are inclusive, contextually relevant, and capable of addressing the unique needs of female farmers.

Based on these findings, the study recommends that the government should domesticate and enforce the National Gender Policy in Agriculture to promote gender-responsive planning, budgeting, and evaluation within the FCT. Strengthening institutional frameworks and ensuring women's representation in agricultural councils, cooperatives, and leadership roles are essential for achieving sustainable gender equality. Additionally, there is a need for increased funding, awareness campaigns, and collaboration among government agencies, NGOs, and local communities to ensure effective program delivery and monitoring. Tailored training, mentorship, and financial support systems should be integrated into capacity-building initiatives to empower female farmers and enhance their productivity and socio-economic resilience.

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